

Does hand movement speed have a linear relationship with the tone of the surface electromyography (SEMG) signal?

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Abstract— Natural hand movements are a current research topic. It has employed tools to analyse surface electromyographic signals associated with each move and its main features. Previous works focused on classifying types of hand movements and searching the relationship of SEMG with force and velocity. However, the described relationship in previous works is in other domains (no time domain). This study evaluates 14 healthy subjects and six types of movements (pronation, supination, ulnar deviation, radial deviation, flexion, and extension -84 records of SEMG and Velocity). The objective was to obtain a linear model (time domain) focused on predicting the velocity of each movement. The results show models strongly linear, with high differences between each movement type, high determination coefficients (0.95 average), and RMSE of 21,18%.

Keywords — *SMEG-Speed model, Hand Moves, linear models*

I. Introduction

Many previous works have sought to relate the surface electromyography (sEMG) signal with the characteristics (speed and force) of the dynamics of hand movement[1]–[3]. Others have considered the problem only as a problem to classify of movements type problem, which has good results [4]–[9]. However, the classification is not enough. Therefore, research is development to improve the explanation of the dynamic features of moves. This way, motivation in different works is to achieve natural hand movements with dynamic features close to natural moves [10]–[15]. Therefore, the orientation is to obtain models for easy myoelectric control of hand moves[16]–[20]. Nevertheless, the relationship between SEMG signals and velocity and force looks like a nonlinear model, which makes difficult future hardware implementation. [1], [3], [13], [20]–[23]. Previous work found a linear relationship between the force and sEMG tone signal [24]. Here, we present the possible linear relationship between velocity and tone of sEMG signals measured from the forearm in six hand movements. The results of our work that we now present could be to easily future hardware implementation.

II. Materials and methods

We studied the following moves: flexion-extension, prone-supination, ulnar deviation-radial deviation. So, the database has 42 sEMG and velocity records taken from 7 healthy

subjects. We calculate the envelope of sEMG using the moving average windowing. We use an algorithm previously validated [18], [19] to obtain speed profiles. The model uses a custom-made tool in MATLAB for model coefficient calculations. All details of the signal processing will be in the following sections.

A. Data acquisition

We used the ML880 PowerLab data acquisition system and the ML135 Dual Bio Amp signal conditioner to visualize it on a PC using the LabChart graphical interface by ADINSTRUMENTS for the sEMG records. The sampling rate for the sEMG signals record was 960 Hz. We use the process shown in Figure 1, employing a 960 frames/s sampling rate for speed profile calculation.

We obtained the sEMG envelope using a movil average of 2 samples in 20ms windows. Figure 2 shows an example of the similarity of both signals (sEMG envelope and Speed profile).

B. Test protocol

The test consists of three sessions: flexion extension, prone-supination, and radio-ular deviation. In the flexion-extension session, the subject is positioned with elbow flexion at 90°, hand pronated, and shoulder abduction at 45°. It performs two repetitions of the flexion and extension movement.

In the prone-supination session, the same procedure was applied, except for the location of the subject, who is seated with elbow and shoulder flexion at 90° and the elbow immobilized, with the anterior face of the hand oriented towards the center of the body (oriented towards a sagittal plane).

Finally, in the last session (radio-ular deviation), the procedures are repeated above, but with elbow flexion to 90°, shoulder abduction to 45°, and hand pronation.

C. Modelling

We proposed a linear relationship between velocity and sEMG tone signal (envelope) using the model proposed according to equation (1), where a and b are model parameters,

and t is the time variable. In Figure 3, you can see the possible relation between the Velocity profile and envelope sEMG signals.

Fig1. Upper panel (process of image). Lower panel (example of markers of flexion-extension move)

$$Velocity(t) = a * SEMGTONE(t) + b \quad (1)$$

We calculated and reported both the model parameters and the bondage of the model (R^2) using IQR values. Table 1 shows the results for all movements. Curve fitting was applied in each subject and each move.

TABLE 1. Comparison of coefficients to each move.

Move	a	b	R^2
	median (IQR)	median (IQR)	
Pronation	4536 (4448, 4624)	23.93 (19.54, 28.31)	0.9092
Supination	0.451 (0.445, 0.458)	106.3 (103.9, 108.7)	0.9468
Flexion	10.18 (10.08, 10.29)	-51.1 (-53.9, -48.3)	0.9714
Extension	1056 (1044, 1069)	-118.1 (-122.4, -113.9)	0.9648
Ulnar deviation	3.32 (3.28, 3.36)	49.88 (48.87, 50.88)	0.9711
Radial deviation	5.47 (5.39, 5.56)	-70.1 (-72.8, -67.5)	0.9369

Fig2. Upper panel (SEMG envelope). Lower panel (speed profile, flexion-extension move)

Fig3. Relationship between Velocity and SEMG tone signals

III. Results

Table 1 is a summary of the linear model fit results. Comparison between model output and measured output was our validation process. The used metric was root mean squared error (RMSE) to quantify the differences. Figure 4 shows an example (pronation) of the behavior of the output model and compares it with the measured original tone. We obtained RMSE globally for all samples (42 records and output model signals). The RMSE was 21,18%.

Fig3. Comparison between model response (red) and measured velocity(green) in pronation movement.

IV. Conclusion

The relationship between surface electromyography tone and velocity profiles is strongly linear. However, there is a scattered behavior of the parameters of the linear model. Also, the difference between subjects and type of movement generates different parameters in each model with considerable dispersions. Therefore, the methodology must be used in each situation, which makes it difficult to apply a general model in hardware that replicates the speeds estimated from the SEMG treatment. However, the global RMS has not been high and could be compensated by a control system that rejects these uncertainties.

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